

AN EXAMPLE OF THE USE OF BIO-DESIGN IN THE INTERIOR OF AN APARTMENT

A person throughout his life always strives to live and surround himself with aesthetic things and create a harmonious environment, both in his home and at the workplace. It helps to maintain psychological comfort and add inspiration, both during work and during rest. When it comes to interior design, biodesign can offer a number of benefits. Let's highlight a few of them:

- **Improved air quality.** Biodesign can help improve indoor air quality by incorporating natural materials and plants into the design. Plants, for example, can absorb pollutants from the air, helping to purify it.
- **Increasing well-being.** Biophilic design, which is a type of biodesign, focuses on incorporating natural elements into the built environment to improve human well-being. Studies have shown that being in nature can reduce stress, lower blood pressure and improve overall mood.
- **Environmental friendliness.** By using sustainable materials and methods, biodesign can help reduce the environmental impact of interior design. For example, materials such as bamboo and cork are renewable and can be harvested without causing long-term damage to the environment.
- **Aesthetic appeal.** Biodesign can help create a beautiful and visually interesting interior using natural forms, colors and patterns. This can help create a more calming and relaxing environment that promotes productivity and creativity.
- **Productivity improvement.** Biophilic interior design can also increase productivity by improving mood and reducing stress levels. Studies have shown that being in nature can improve concentration and cognitive function, which can lead to better productivity.

The work presents an example of visualization of an apartment project using biodesign using the 3ds Max (3D Studio MAX) software product. Figure 1 shows a visualization of part of the interior project of the apartment "Fire place and fountain" using bionic elements of fire and water.

Rice. 1 "Fire place and fountain"

This project shows a terrace on which approximately 20 people can be placed, who will be able to relax and enjoy the aesthetics and appeal of a beautiful and visually interesting interior, in which natural forms are used, this will help to create a more soothing and relaxing environment. In this project, 2 main human elements are implemented, which he can look at without taking his eyes off: fire and water. Under such conditions, a person feels as comfortable as possible.

Thus, when designing the interior of an apartment, to create the psychological comfort of future residents, designers often use elements of biodesign for their harmonious and healthy environment. The work shows the advantages and examples of the use of natural bionic elements in the visualization of the interior of the apartment, which will contribute to the productivity and creativity of the people who will live there.